

A NOVEL TEST METHOD FOR EVALUATING DEWATERING OF FIBER MIXTURES USED FOR MOLDED PULP PACKAGING PRODUCTION

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Abstract: *The shift toward sustainable and circular materials in packaging has intensified interest in molded pulp products as eco-friendly alternatives to plastics. Since multiple factors affect the efficiency of the pulp molding process, it is essential to understand each step in detail and to evaluate how process parameters can be influenced by fiber type, blends, or additives. Among these, dewatering behavior during the forming process is one of the most critical parameters for product quality and production efficiency. To investigate this, a custom-built laboratory device was developed to analyze fiber mixtures under vacuum-assisted drainage conditions. The device measures two primary parameters in real time: applied vacuum pressure and cumulative water mass drained. The obtained data enable the characterization of drainage dynamics in fiber suspensions and provide a practical framework for comparing the dewatering efficiency of different raw material blends. In this study, the first results of the dewatering tests with the lab-testing device, together with the main fiber properties of the investigated material mixtures, are presented and discussed. The work focuses on mixtures composed mainly of recycled paper and fresh fibers – materials commonly used in molded pulp applications. The results contribute to a deeper process understanding and support future improvements in sustainable packaging production.*

Keywords: molded pulp, packaging technology, test method, dewatering efficiency, cellulosic material

1 INTRODUCTION

Molded pulp packaging—produced by shaping recycled paper fibers into protective forms—is increasingly recognized as a sustainable alternative to plastic and Styrofoam. The market for molded pulp packaging is growing rapidly, fueled by rising consumer demand for eco-friendly solutions and stricter regulations on single-use plastics (Semple et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2022; Su et al., 2018). Today, molded pulp products are generally classified by their manufacturing methods. According to the International Molded Fiber Association (IMFA), they fall into four categories: (1) thick wall, (2) transfer, (3) thermoformed, and (4) processed (Dey et al., 2020; Didone et al., 2017; Freville et al., 2024; Su et al., 2018).

1. Thermoforming – This method is a very widely applied manufacturing technique in industry. The process generally consists of four stages: the material is first shaped within a cold mold, then compacted in a heated mold, further densified, and finally dried. A key benefit of thermoforming is that it eliminates the need for an additional drying step in an oven. The resulting products exhibit high dimensional quality, smooth surface finishes, and wall thicknesses typically between 2 and 4 mm, sometimes even down to 1 mm.

2. Transfer molding – This approach requires both a forming mold and a transfer (or take-off) mold, in addition to a drying oven. The products manufactured through transfer molding usually possess uniform surfaces on both sides and wall thicknesses ranging from 3 to 5 mm.
3. Thick-wall molding – In this process, an open mold is employed, and the molded pieces are subsequently dried in an oven. The feedstock often includes Kraft fibers combined with recycled paper. The finished products show a contrast in surface texture: the inner surface is comparatively smooth, while the outer surface remains coarse. Typical wall thicknesses vary between 5 and 10 mm.
4. Processed molding – This category covers molded pulp products that undergo post-processing treatments, such as coating, printing, or the incorporation of functional additives (Didone et al., 2017).

For nearly 30 years molded pulp products were mainly used for egg trays, but today their applications have become more diverse (Gavazzo et al., 2005). Molded pulp packaging type is already widely used across sectors such as food, transportation, construction, healthcare, and household goods. The applications of this packaging type depend on whether it is required solely to protect products from external influences or also to provide cushioning. However, the effects of additives, material blends, and process parameters on production efficiency and product quality are not yet fully understood, which limits technical advancements in pulp molding. To address this gap, the present work introduces initial results from dewatering tests using a new method designed to evaluate the dewatering efficiency of material mixtures, aiming to reflect their behavior in molded pulp production.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Raw materials

The raw materials employed in this study are already used industrially for producing molded pulp packaging via the thermoforming process. For the initial trials, two pulp suspensions were prepared. Mixture 1 consisted of unused corrugated board (class 4.01.02) combined with ECF-bleached long-fiber sulphate pulp. Mixture 2 contained the same pulp in combination with GC1, a pigment-coated virgin mechanical pulp board with a white reverse side.

2.2 Fiber analysis

To characterize the different kinds of raw materials, morphological Fiber Tester measurements were conducted to know the fiber shape (curl), the fines content and the average fiber length. For this, the L&W Fiber Tester Plus device from ABB (Zürich, Switzerland) was used to analyze fiber dimensions, as well as the fiber form, from which the mean kink-index and kink-angle were acquired.

2.3 Freeness of pulp (Canadian standard method)

The Canadian Standard Freeness (CSF) test, performed in accordance with TAPPI T 227, was used to evaluate the drainage rate of dilute pulp suspensions. This method measures the volume of water discharged from a standardized freeness tester after a 3 g/L pulp suspension drains through a perforated screen under controlled conditions.

2.4 Lab-testing device

A laboratory-scale drainage test bench (see Figure 1) was developed to replicate the forming station of pulp molding machines, excluding the 3D-formed mold at this stage. This setup enables small-scale testing, thereby avoiding the high energy and material costs associated with full-scale TPM machinery. The system consists of two primary containers: a vacuum container (1), where the required vacuum is generated, and an intermediate container (2) with a removable sieve structure, which is connected to an upper attachment where the pulp suspension is introduced (3). To simulate the vacuum drainage process seen in industrial machines while maintaining a decoupled and controllable laboratory setup, a pneumatic ball valve (4) is installed between the vacuum and intermediate containers. This valve, connected via a hose (5), allows controlled initiation of the vacuum suction. Additionally, a pressure sensor (6) is integrated into the vacuum container to record the vacuum profile during each test. A scale (7) located beneath the entire apparatus continuously logs the mass change, providing a time-resolved drainage curve.

Figure 3: Scheme of the lab-testing device for the dewatering measurements. (1) vacuum container; (2) intermediate container with removable sieve structure; (3) upper container for adding the pulp suspension; (4) pneumatic valve with the connecting hose (5); (6) pressure sensor; (7) scale.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before starting the measurements with the lab-testing device, the fiber properties of the material mixtures were analyzed. Of particular interest are the fiber length distribution (length-weighted) and the Canadian Standard Freeness (CSF) values. These parameters provide an initial estimation of how the raw material suspension will behave—first in the forming station of the pulp molding machines, and second during the dewatering test with the self-built dewatering device.

Table 1 summarizes the fiber properties, including the CSF values of the investigated raw material mixtures. The fiber length distribution (length-weighted) is illustrated in Figure 2. By combining these results, it becomes evident that mixture 1 should dewater more slowly than mixture 2, which can be attributed to its higher CSF value despite the measured fines content was slightly lower in mixture 1.

Table 5: Summary of the fiber properties of mixture 1 and mixture 2.

sample	mixture 1	mixture 2
Fiber length numeric Ln [mm]	0.779	0.825
Fiber length (length weighted) Lw [mm]	1.4	1.4
Fiber length (weight weighted) Lz [mm]	2.205	2.176
Fiber width [μm]	24.2	24.4
Fine content (length weighted) Lw [%]	46.75	47.73
Kink index [-]	1.463	1.498
Kink angle [°]	50.7	50.1
CSF	617	744
Fine percentage [%]	97.3	97.5

Figure 4: Length weighted fiber distribution of the two used pulp suspensions

After the fiber properties of the material mixtures had been analyzed, dewatering tests of the two mixtures with the same concentrations were carried out on the new lab-testing device, as it was shown in Figure 1. For these measurements a concentration of 5g o.d. fibers in 2L was used (see Figure 3).

Figure 5: Comparison of dewatering behavior of the two mixtures with the lab-testing device. Dotted lines show the progress of the vacuum pressure, while the continuous lines represent the mass of the drained water during the measurements.

The conducted measurements, presented in Figure 3, confirmed the expected trend: mixture 1, characterized by a lower CSF value, exhibited slower dewatering compared to mixture 2, which had a higher CSF value. This behavior is consistent with observations in pulp molding machines, supporting the conclusion that the laboratory testing device yields reliable data.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a novel test method for investigating the behavior of different material mixtures and raw materials during dewatering with applied vacuum was presented. Combined with the characterization of fiber properties, this approach should provide a better understanding of the dewatering step in the forming station of pulp molding machines.

The first measurements yielded promising results: the same trends observed in pulp molding machines could be reproduced in the lab-testing device. In particular, the fiber properties—especially the CSF value—correlated well with the measured dewatering behavior. Future measurements will be carried out using different sieve structures, concentrations and additives.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the developed test method can improve process understanding in pulp molding and support practical advancements in sustainable packaging production, contributing to more efficient manufacturing practices.

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